

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.24

Workpackage 6

Responsible Partner: BfR, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP6.24 Web-content developed
Project Acronym	JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE
Author	Tamino Dubbert (BfR), Marie Sjölund (SVA)
Other contributors	
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Confidential until publication.....
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

BIOPIGEE

Web-content disseminated

Task leading institute

BfR, SVA

Objective

The BIOPIGEE project went out to investigate and identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures against *Salmonella* and HEV in pig farming across Europe. Apart from the scientific endeavor, it was a goal to inform not only the scientific community but to make project results, outputs and insights available to all stakeholders and the non-scientific community.

Overview of project web-content now and in the future

All project results (papers and posters), deliverables and outputs are already or will be listed and linked on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE webpage (<https://onehealthjp.eu/jrp-biopigee/>) and on the Zenodo webpage (<https://zenodo.org/>). Only exceptions are the papers that are still in the process of writing and that will be published in 2023. After their publication, they will be added to the OHEJP BIOPIGEE and the Zenodo webpage. The slaughterhouse guidance manual (project output) will only be made available to the public, after the associated paper is published in 2023. '

Overview of web-content (links to appendix)

[Deliverables](#)

[Publications](#) (currently available and pending)

[Posters](#)

[Presentations](#)

[Outputs](#)

[Workshops as events](#)

[Project press releases](#)

[Websites for dissemination](#)

Dissemination of web-content

Dissemination was achieved by the workshops throughout the project and the information material sent to farming schools and multipliers. The *workshops* over the course of the project period served to disseminate early findings, to get feedback from stakeholders, to present preliminary and final results, and to provide a platform for discussion about future research and stakeholder needs. The *information material* in PDF-format introduces to the project, project goals, outputs, and links to the BIOPIGEE webpage and other helpful websites, and provides compact knowledge about effective biosecurity measures.

Besides the workshop series and the information material, the public and stakeholders have been made aware of the project and its work by individual talks and presentations of the project partners on conferences, as well as by press releases about the project by the participating institutes on their respective websites .

Workshops

Originally, three workshops were planned as one-day in-person events in conjunction to relevant conferences. The objective of the first workshop was to gather input from stakeholders and to inform about the project within the first half year of the project. The objective of the second workshop was to disseminate preliminary results from the project and to adjust data collection in running studies according to input from stakeholders. During the third workshop the objective was to disseminate results from the project, to receive feedback and discuss implementation. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the format of the first workshop was changed to several small national, partly online events to connect researchers with stakeholders. The implementation of the other workshops were delayed and changed to online events organised and held by the partner institutes independently of other conferences. The third workshop covered the topics and results related to primary production, and an additional fourth workshop was held shortly after to focus specifically on the results regarding slaughterhouses.

Information Material

The objective of the information material for farming schools was to provide a document with information about the BIOPIGEE project, the pathogens, the outputs and about examples of effective biosecurity measures against *Salmonella* and HEV based on the project work.

For the dissemination of the information material, websites and farming schools and farming universities have been selected and/or contacted. With the end of the project, the information material will be provided to:

- 20+ websites and online channels collected in WP6.1.1
- 16+ contact partners at the partner institutes
- 100+ farming schools/colleges/universities from five countries

Translations

All project outputs (checklists, slaughterhouse guidance manual, cost-efficiency support tool, and information material) have been translated from English into Bulgarian, Czech, Dutch, Estonian, German, Italian, and Polish, using the commercial version of the software deepl (<https://www.deepl.com/translator>). The original and licensed English outputs will be available on Zenodo.org together with the translations.

Conclusion

By the workshops and national events alone more than 1000 interested people could be reached. The information material will be provided to more than 130 websites, channels, and multipliers. Together, these efforts will bring further awareness to the results of the BIOPIGEE project, and the topics of biosecurity and One Health, especially beyond the scientific community.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

APPENDIX

Deliverables

Task	Deliverable	Name	Link
2.1	D-JRP21-WP2.1	Biosecurity protocol (addressing Salmonella and HEV) designed for data collection in the field	https://zenodo.org/record/5336900
6.1	D-JRP21-WP6.4	BIOPIGEE flyer prepared	https://zenodo.org/record/4009015
1.2	D-JRP21-WP1.2	First draft of data management plan finished	
1.3	D-JRP21-WP1.4	Project report 1 st year submitted	https://zenodo.org/record/4361090
3.3	D-JRP21-WP3.6	HEV infectivity assay available	https://zenodo.org/record/5242819
3.3	D-JRP21-WP3.5	Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers	https://zenodo.org/record/4940091
3.1	D-JRP21-WP3.7	Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	https://zenodo.org/record/5211242
6.3	D-JRP21-WP6.10	Workshop 2 completed	https://zenodo.org/record/5806257
1.3	D-JRP21-WP1.13	Project report 2 nd year submitted	https://zenodo.org/record/5930342
2.2	D-JRP21-WP2.9	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm	https://zenodo.org/record/5792859
2.3	D-JRP21-WP2.8	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses	https://zenodo.org/record/5774876
3.3	D-JRP21-WP3.20	HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm	https://zenodo.org/record/5793040
6.1	D-JRP21-WP6.15	Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided	https://zenodo.org/record/5772529
2.4	D-JRP21-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	https://zenodo.org/record/6780124
3.2	D-JRP21-WP3.19	Information on the effect of different disinfectants on salmonella in biofilm	https://zenodo.org/record/7023490
3.3	D-JRP21-WP3.14	Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm	https://zenodo.org/record/7231931
4.2	D-JRP21-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures	https://zenodo.org/record/6974303
6.3	D-JRP21-WP6.3	Workshop 1 completed	https://zenodo.org/record/6974588

2.5	D-JRP21-WP2.18	Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of Hepatitis E to HEVnet	https://zenodo.org/record/7267862
4.4	D-JRP21-WP4.16	Economic calculation	https://zenodo.org/record/7085855
4.3	D-JRP21-WP4.17	Model output: Number of human cases with and without biosecurity measures	https://zenodo.org/record/7180805
5.5	D-JRP21-WP5.21	Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice finished and forwarded to WP1 and WP6	https://zenodo.org/record/7268326
6.1	D-JRP21-WP6.22	Information for farming schools provided	https://zenodo.org/record/7429810
6.3	D-JRP21-WP6.26	Workshop 3 completed	https://zenodo.org/record/7259005
6.3	D-JRP21-WP6.28	Workshop 4 completed	https://zenodo.org/record/7181040
1.2	D-JRP21-WP1.19	Revised data management plan submitted	https://zenodo.org/record/7429754
1.3	D-JRP21-WP1.23	Final project report submitted	https://zenodo.org/record/7429770
6.1	D-JRP21-WP6.24	Project web-content disseminated	https://zenodo.org/record/7429783
6.2	D-JRP21-WP6.25	A support tool (Excel) for calculation of cost effectiveness of preventive biosecurity measures developed	https://zenodo.org/record/7429826
6.2	D-JRP21-WP6.27	Provision of biosecurity protocol and of benchmark of biosecurity practice	https://zenodo.org/record/7351107

Publications

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status
Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière: analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation, JRP conference/paper DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6091598 https://zenodo.org/record/6091598	published
Complex network analysis to understand trading partnership in French swine production, PlosOne DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0266457 https://zenodo.org/record/6458445#.YnkdKehBxwQ	published
What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for animal production and linked processing operations DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100433 https://zenodo.org/record/7143533	published
Prioritization of pig farm biosecurity for control of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus infections; results of a European Expert Opinion Elicitation	submitted
Effectiveness of pig farm biosecurity measures for the control of Salmonella on European farms – a case control study	submitted
Detection of HEV RNA by one-step real-time RT-PCR in far-row-to-finish pig farms in Bulgaria	submitted
Slaughterhouse biosecurity measures for Salmonella control with quantified effectiveness: a review	under preparation
Review of the implementation of effective biosecurity practices, related to Salmonella and hepatitis E virus control, in a selection of European pig slaughterhouses	under preparation
A quantitative microbiological risk assessment for transmission of HEV in the pork production chain.	under preparation
Surveillance of Hepatitis E virus circulation in Italian pig farms	under preparation
Sequence diversity of Hepatitis E virus from European pig farms	under preparation
Protective Biosecurity Measures to reduce hepatitis E virus in European pig farms	under preparation
Biosecurity measures reducing Salmonella spp., hepatitis E virus and pathogenic Escherichia coli prevalence in pig farms: A systematic review and meta-analysis.	under preparation

Posters

- Jones, H., Smith, R.P., Burow, E., on behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Alborali G., Guadagno F., Delibato E., Treglia I., De Sabato L., Monini M., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Molecular tracing of dissemination routes of *Salmonella* spp, Hepatitis E virus and other viruses as fecal indicators in pigs at slaughterhouse. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646338>
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Aprea G., Romantini R., Alborali G., D'Angelantonio D., Garofolo G., Scattolini S., De Sabato L., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Presence of *Salmonella* spp. And Hepatitis E virus in Italian pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6638970>
- Meester M., Tobias T., Meulenbroek C., Hakze-van der Honing R., van Oort S., Bouwknecht M., Stegeman A., van der Poel W.H.M. (2022). Prevalence of HEV in finishing pigs: cross-sectional exploration of farm specific patterns and evaluation of sampling. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566927>
- Kozyra, I., Zając, M., Żmudzki, J., Dors, A., Skrzypiec, E., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A. (2022). Epidemiological significance of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) occurrence in fattening pigs in Poland. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673709>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2021). Multi-levels Hepatitis E Virus Spread In Various Epidemiological Contexts: Combining Complex Network Analysis & Disease Transmission Model. Poster at the 8th International Conference on Infectious Disease Dynamics (Epidemics 8), online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786494>
- Huber, N., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu, E. L., Prigge, C., Käsbohrer, A., Andraud, M., D'Angelantonio, D., Viltrop, A., Niine, T., Hammami, P., Zmudzki, J., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for farms and linked processing operations. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Smith, R., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). *Salmonella* presence on European pig farms. I3S International Symposium *Salmonella* & Salmonellosis 20.-22.06.222. Saint-Malo. <https://zenodo.org/record/7054296>
- Dors, A., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A., Karbowski, P., Szalkowski, W., Zmudzki, J. (2022). A survey on external biosecurity in selected commercial Polish pig farms. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Burow, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Tobias, T., Sassu, E. L., Galpó, E., Prigge, C., Smith, R. P., Sjölund, M. (2022). Expert opinion on biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in pig farming - findings of the OHEJP BIOPIGEE project. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). The best biosecurity practices in European abattoirs in regards to *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online. <https://zenodo.org/record/7032155>
- Jones, H., Smith, R. P., Burow, E. (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.

- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Biosecurity practices to reduce risk of hepatitis E virus in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Sensitivity and specificity of pen-level sampling methods for hepatitis E virus detection in fattening pigs. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Osland, A.M, Oastler, C. Brook, E. Gosling, B. Arvand, M. Richter, A.M, Konrat, K. Asal, B. Vestby. L.K. (2022). Effect of Glutaraldehyde on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella*. Poster will be presented at Eurobiofilms 2022. 31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Multi-levels hepatitis E virus spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission model. Poster at the Epidemics conference. <https://zenodo.org/record/5786494>
- Hammami, P (2021). Live animal movement - Understnad trade partners choices to predict cahins of contact. SVEPM 2021.
- McCarthy, C. (2021). BIOPIGEE: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures. OHEJP ASM 2021.
- Bester, C. (2022). Development of an economic model to assess the cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures to reduce the burden of Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus in the pork production chain. ISAH 2022.

Oral presentations

- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Biosecurity measures in European slaughterhouses to prevent the contamination of pig carcasses with *Salmonella*. Konverentsi "terve loom ja tervislik toit 2022" artiklikogumik (Estonian conference), 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6355316>
- Viltrop, A. (2022). Biosecurity of *Salmonella* from Estonian pig farms perspective. Estonian Officials Veterinarian Training day.
- Burow, E. (presentation), Zoche-Golob, V. (abstract), Aprea, G., Sjölund, M., for the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Biosecurity measures reducing Hepatitis E Virus in pig herds – findings of the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. Oral presentation at German conference 22. Fachtagung für Fleisch- und Geflügelfleischhygiene, 1.-2. March 2022, Berlin, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6524126>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Spread of hepatitis E virus from pens to the national industry: complex network analysis and modelling. 54th Journées de la Recherche Porcine (JRP), 2nd February 2022, online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091598>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière : analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation. Talk at the Junior Researcher Programme conference <https://zenodo.org/record/6091598>
- Burow, E., N. Huber, E. Galipó, R. Smith (2022). Effective and prioritised biosecurity practice to control *Salmonella* in pig farming - findings from the BIOPIGEE project. Oral presentation at HealthyLivestock conference, 16.06.2022, hybrid
- Burow, E., Schulze-Horsel, T., Harlizius, J., Rostalski, A., Smith, R., Zoche-Golob, V., Galipó, E., Waller, E., Jones, H., Sjölund, M., Käsbohrer, A. (2022). Biosicherheitsmaßnahmen zur Kontrolle von Salmonellen und Hepatitis E Viren in der europäischen Schweinehaltung - OHEJP Projekt BIOPIGEE. Biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in European pig farming - OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. DACH Epidemiologietagung 2022, 31.08.-02.09.2022, Oldenburg.
- Galipó, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu E. L., Prigge, C., Sjölund, M., Tobias, T., Rzezutka, A., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Pig farm biosecurity for control of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus infections – a survey of European experts. Oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Complex network analysis and Exponential Random Graph Models: Epidemiological implications of network structures. Modah 2021.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Multi-level Hepatitis E Virus Spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission models. CCS 2021.
- Wilkins, N. (2022). A farm-to-consumption quantitative microbiological risk assessment for hepatitis E in pigs. Presented at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.

Outputs

Name	Content	Availability on Zenodo.org	Linked on BIOPIGEE website
Glossary	Glossary to harmonize and clarify terms for research in farm biosecurity, pig farming, epidemiology, slaughterhouse biosecurity, slaughterhouse procedure	Link	Yes
Biosecurity protocol	Questionnaire on biosecurity measures with high relevance for the control of <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV	Link	Coming in 2023
Checklist for <i>Salmonella</i>	Checklist containing evidence-based biosecurity measures against <i>Salmonella</i> on pig farms for self assessment	Link	Coming in 2023
Checklist for HEV	Checklist containing evidence-based biosecurity measures against HEV on pig farms for self assessment	Link	Coming in 2023
Slaughterhouse guidance manual	Manual with evidence-based recommendations on slaughterhouse practices to control <i>Salmonella</i>	Link (publicly available after publication in 2023)	Coming in 2023
Cost-efficiency support tool	Tool to perform cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and estimate benefit-cost ratio (BCR) for twelve biosecurity measures against <i>Salmonella</i> or HEV in pig farming	Link	Coming in 2023
Information material for farming schools	Information for education purposes on the BIOPIGEE project, <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV, project outputs, links, as well as examples of good biosecurity	Link	Coming in 2023

Workshops

Workshop Number	National event/Host	Purpose	Format	Participants	BIOPIGEE members	Link to deliverable
Workshop 1	German Event	Event of the North Rhine-Westphalian Pig Health Service	2-day-hybrid event	Ca. 100	1	https://zenodo.org/record/6974588
	Estonian Event 1	Annual conference of the Institute of the Veterinary Medicine and Animal Sciences of the Estonian University of Life Sciences 'Healthy Animal – Healthy Food'	Presence	>200	2	
	Estonian Event 2	Seminar for the animal health officials from the headquarter and regional offices of the Agriculture and Food Board in Estonia	Presence	27	2	
	Polish Event	XVI Congress of the Polish Society of Veterinary Sciences	2-day-hybrid event	495	2	
Workshop 2	Hosted by SVA	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity measures to control Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) along the pig production chain in Europe	Online	62	35	https://zenodo.org/record/5806257
Workshop 3	Hosted by BfR	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity Measures to Control Salmonella and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) in European Primary Pig Production	Online	153	26	https://zenodo.org/record/7259005
Workshop 4	Hosted by	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses to Control Salmonella and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV)	Online	79	10	https://zenodo.org/record/7181040

Project Press Releases

Institute	Language	Link
BfR	German	https://www.bfr.bund.de/de/biosicherheitspraktiken_fuer_die_schweinehaltung_in_europa_ejp_biopigee_-_252634.html
BfR	English	https://www.bfr.bund.de/en/biosecurity_practises_for_pig_farming_across_europe_ejp_biopigee_-_252636.html
BfR	English	https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/695510
RKI	German	https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Institut/OrgEinheiten/Abt1/FG14/BIOPIGEE.html
SVA	Swedish	https://www.sva.se/amnesomraden/forskning/internationellt-samarbete/europeisk-samverkan-kring-livsmedelsburna-smittor/biopigee-ett-one-health-ejp-projekt/
VFL	Estonian	https://www.vetlab.ee/et/projektid/bioturvalisuse-praktikad-Euroopa-seafarmidele-BIOPIGEE
APHA	English	https://twitter.com/APHAgovuk/status/1402585096918605828
APHA	English	https://www.pig-world.co.uk/news/apha-seeks-pig-farmers-for-biosecurity-study.html
PIWet	Polish	https://www.piwet.pulawy.pl/oferta/3
PIWet	Polish	http://xvi-kongres-ptnw.wmw.sggw.pl/program/

Websites for Dissemination

Organisation	Website address	Country	Stakeholder (i.e authorities, vets, retailers, farmers)	BIOPIGEE Partner
SVA National Veterinary Institute	https://www.sva.se/	SE	General public to authorities	SVA
Swedish biosecurity programme for pigs	http://www.xn--smittskra-02a.se/gris/smittsakrad-besattning-gris/	SE	Farmers	SVA
BfR German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment	https://www.bfr.bund.de/de/start.html	DE	General public to authorities	BfR
	www.izs.it	IT	General public to authorities	IZSAM
	www.izsler.it	IT	General public to authorities	IZSLER
AHDB-Pork	https://pork.ahdb.org.uk/	UK	farmers, pig industry levy payers = processors and pig producers	APHA
Pig World	http://www.pig-world.co.uk/	UK	Farmers, Pig producers, pig industry and allied industries	APHA
Farmers weekly	https://www.fwi.co.uk/	UK	Farmers, Livestock keepers, pig industry and allied industries	APHA
Pig333	https://www.pig333.com/	N/A	Vets, farmers	APHA
The pigsite	https://thepigsite.com/	N/A	Vets, farmers	APHA
Farmers Guardian	https://www.fginsight.com/	UK	authorities,vets, retailers, farmers	APHA
National Pig Association	http://www.npa-uk.org.uk/	UK	branch of National Farmers Union, a members association of commercial pig producers and a lobby group for the pig industry	APHA
APHA blogs	https://aphascience.blog.gov.uk/	UK	Authorities, vets, retailers, farmers, pig industry	APHA
Pig topics	http://www.positiveaction.info/magdetails.php?m=4	N/A	authorities, vets, retailers, farmers (international)	APHA
British Pig Association	https://britishpigs.org.uk/	UK	members association of pedigree pig keepers	APHA
Pig Veterinary Society	https://www.pigvetsoc.org.uk/	UK	Vets	APHA
Pig Progress	https://www.pigprogress.net/	UK	Vets, farmers, pig industry and allied industries	APHA
Estonian Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL)	http://www.vetlab.ee/	EE	Authorities, vets, farmers	VFL
Estonian Pig Breeding Association	https://www.estpig.ee/	EE	Pig producers, farmers, pig industry	VFL
Estonian Veterinary Association	https://vet.ee/	EE	Vets	VFL
Veterinary and Food board (will be reformed into "Agriculture and Food Board" from 1 January 2021)	https://vet.agri.ee/	EE	Authorities, vets, retailers, farmers	VFL